

Influence of Compensation and Working Condition on Job Satisfaction and Commitment of Lecturers at the College

Muslim Ansori^{a*}, Christa Caroline^b

^a*Jurusan Manajemen Bisnis, Politeknik Negeri Batam, ansori.wae@gmail.com, Indonesia*

^b*Jurusan Manajemen Bisnis, Politeknik Negeri Batam, christasimarmata01@gmail.com, Indonesia*

Abstract. This study aims to investigate about the influence of compensation and working conditions on job satisfaction and commitment of lecturers at the college. Job satisfaction and commitment of lecturers at the college so need to be considered in carrying out any activities undertaken by the lecturer, without job satisfaction and commitment of the lecturers at the college will lower spirit of lecturers. Respondents in this study is a lecturer of accounting and management, there are 156 lecturers were taken as samples. Techniques determination of the sample using the slovin formula. This study uses a simple linear regression analysis. The results of this study indicate that the compensation effect on job satisfaction, compensation effect on commitment of lecturers at the college, working condition effect on job satisfaction, and working conditions has no effect the commitment of lecturers at the college.

Keywords: financial performance, profitability, capital structure, islamic banks

Introduction

The college is an educational organization. The success of an organization of education in running the educational activity is inseparable factors of human resources (HR). HR plays an important role as the spearhead of an organization, especially organizations working in the field of services. HR professionals are used by the organization to run the operation well and achieve all the objectives set. One of the HR working in the college are educators or usually called by the lecturers.

According to Law No. 14 of 2005 on teachers and lecturers, lecturers are professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing and disseminating science, technology, and the arts through education, research, and community service. Quality education is almost impossible without the satisfaction and commitment of the lecturers (Islam et al., 2012). Lecturer is an important asset to the college, without a lecturer who

teaches learners, the educational organizations are not running with effective organizational goals. Lecturer and educational organizations are closely related, the lecturer can have in common understanding will be the achievement of organizational goals to be achieved. Understanding that arise will establish good cooperation between the employee and the organization, the attachment to the organization's commitment to the organizations that have accepted them as an employee. Employees with a high level of commitment will show optimal results.

Robbins and Judge (2008), reveals that employee commitment (lecturer) in the organization is an emotional connection with employees of certain organizations to set goals and a desire to remain a member and the achievement of the goals of the organization. Job satisfaction is one of the important factors to obtain optimal results and accountable. When a feeling of satisfaction in the work of course he would work as closely as possible with all the capabilities they have to complete the job assignment

*Corresponding author. E-mail: ansori.wae@gmail.com

(Johan, 2002), thus the productivity and the work of employees will be increased optimally.

Supporting lecturer commitment to their organization and job satisfaction is the provision of appropriate compensation and adequate working conditions for employees in carrying out the work. Compensation is one of the important factors and concern to many people in retaining employees and attract qualified human resources (Bangun, 2012). Compensation is the reward of the organization for a job well done. If managed properly, the compensation will help the organization to achieve its objectives and obtaining, maintaining, and keeping employees well, conversely, without adequate compensation, employees that there is very likely to leave the organization (Rivai and Sagala, 2013).

In addition to compensation, comfortable of working conditions and conducive urgently needed by the lecturers to work. The working conditions is a condition that is around employees and can affect the employee in performing their job Luthans (2006). So, if the working conditions are not so comfortable for employees will increase job dissatisfaction and employee commitment (lecturer) at the college will be the minimum goal is reached and not the organization.

This study aimed to test the variable compensation effect on job satisfaction, compensation variables effect on commitment of lecturer at the college, variable working conditions effect on job satisfaction and working conditions variables effect on commitment of lecturer at the college.

Literature Review

Compensation

Rivai and Sagala (2013), compensation is something that employees received in lieu of contributing their services to the company. Compensation is one of the important factors and concern in many organizations in retaining and attracting qualified human resources (Bangun, 2012). The compensation must be based on principles of justice, where compensation can meet the needs of its employees, at least the compensation should be based on the work already done by the employee to the organization being run.

Working Condition

According Luthans (2006) working condition is a condition that is around employees and can affect the employee to do their job. Factors that may affect the working conditions of the employee's performance such as: lighting, comfort, air circulation, and security.

Commitment Lecturer

According to Robbins and Judge (2008), employee commitment (lecturer) in the organization is an emotional connection with employees of certain organizations to set goals and a desire to remain a member, and the achievement of the goals of the organization. Employee commitment (lecturer) at the organization often defined as (1) a strong desire to become a member of the organization, (2) the desire to strive in accordance with the wishes of the organization, (3) a belief in the acceptance of organizational goals (Luthans, 2006). Commitment lecturer at the college is one thing that is important for every individual who works in a university expressed the attitude to recognize and bind them together and achieve organizational objectives. Strong commitment lecturer at the college will show the loyalty of lecturer to survive being an educator in the organization.

Job Satisfaction

According Rivai and Sagala (2013), job satisfaction is basically something individual, each individual has a level of satisfaction varies according to the job assessment imposed on them. The higher the ratings given for the work or activities undertaken so the higher the level of work satisfaction, but someone did devaluing of work then the lower the level satisfaction. Robbins and Judge (2008) job satisfaction as a positive feeling for the work that has been done.

Two Factor Theory

According Bangun (2012), this theory was first proposed by Herzberg (1959), job characteristics can be grouped into two categories, one called "dissatisfies" or "hygiene factors" and the other called the "satisfies" or "motivators". Satisfies is a necessary factor in the employee stating their satisfaction that consists of interesting work, full of challenges, the opportunities for achievement, the opportunity to obtain the award, and promotional opportunities within the organization (Rivai and Sagala, 2013). The

fulfillment of these factors, the employee will be satisfied with their jobs, if not met these factors will lead to job dissatisfaction. Dissatisfies (hygiene factors) are all factors that become a source of dissatisfaction in work, consisting of salary / wages, supervision, interpersonal relations, and working conditions. If these factors are not fulfilled, the employee will not be satisfied. But if these factors are fulfilled by the organization concerned, then the employees will feel satisfied.

Theory of Justice

Rivai and Sagala (2013), the theory of justice suggests that people will feel satisfied or dissatisfied, depending on the presence or absence of justice in a situation that is desired by the employee, particularly in terms of employment. Milkovich et al. (2011) revealed that employees assess fairness in remuneration by making some comparisons, comparing the same job with their work, comparing their work with other employees in the same organization, and comparing the payroll with external salary levels. The results of this comparison depends on accuracy knowledge of employees for such work and internal structure, and external salary levels of other employees. According to this theory there are four components that must be understood is input, results, justice and injustice. Input is a matter that is considered by employees in support of its work, such as: education, experience, skills, the number of tasks and the equipment used to carry out the work. The result is something that is considered valuable by an employee obtained from their work, such as: wages or salaries, fringe benefits, status, awards and the opportunity to succeed or self-actualization. Based on this theory, every employee will compare input ratio themselves with input ratio results of others, if the comparison is considered fair, the employee will be satisfied. But if the comparison is not balanced will arise employee dissatisfaction

Theory of Incompatibility

Rivai and sagala (2013), this theory to measure job satisfaction a person by calculating the difference between something that should have been with the perceived reality. Therefore, when the satisfaction obtained in excess of what is desired, then the person will be more satisfied, then instead of it there is a mismatch, but the positive mismatch. Employee satisfaction depends on the difference between

something that is considered to be achieved by what is achievable.

Theory of Hierarchy of Needs

Robbins and Judge (2008), describing the theory of the hierarchy of needs. According to this theory, there are five hierarchy of needs, namely:

1. Physiological: hunger, thirst, shelter, sexual and other physical needs.
2. Security: curiosity protected from physical danger and emotional.
3. Social: compassion, possession, acceptance and friendship.
4. Awards: factors internal awards such as self-respect, autonomy, and achievement; and factors external rewards such as status, recognition and awards.
5. Self-actualization: the urge to be a person in accordance with these skills; includes growth, the achievement of one's potential and self-fulfillment.

Research conducted by Neog and Barua (2014), which uses some of the determinants of job satisfaction, one of which is compensation. This study found a significant positive relationship between compensation and job satisfaction on employee automobile. Research conducted by Sari (2009), there are two variables that can affect the administration of employee job satisfaction at the British International School. The study reveals that the compensation received by employees and organizational climate together show a positive relationship to job satisfaction.

Research conducted by Bilal (2012), using a university lecturer who worked in Islamabad and Rawalpindi as research objects. This study stated that the influence of the compensation and working conditions on job satisfaction. Research conducted by Haq et al. (2012), using some of the determinants of employee commitment to the organization, one of which is a condition of employment. This study revealed the presence of positive and significant relationship between working conditions on employee commitment to the organization.

Research conducted by Islam et al. (2012), using the university lecturer who work in the state of Punjab in Pakistan as research objects. The study reveals that the influence of compensation on job satisfaction and commitment influence of compensation on faculty at the college. Research conducted by Rizal et al. (2014), the study was conducted in the city of Kendari with the

object of research is the employees who work the area of revenue management. The results in this study revealed that the compensation has a significant effect on employee commitment to the organization. Then, in a study conducted by the Nawab and Bhatti (2011), using the employees working on the Higher Education Commission (HEC) as the object, and reveal that the influence of compensation positive and significant impact on employee commitment to college and job satisfaction.

Compensation Effect on Job Satisfaction

Employees who have worked to contribute energy and thoughts in order to earn a reward or remuneration in accordance with the energy released (Bangun, 2012). One way employers to improve employee job satisfaction is the provision of adequate compensation to employees (Bangun, 2012). That the compensation earned by the employees, the employees will be satisfied with their work in the organization. This is evidenced by other research conducted by Neog and Barua (2014) which states that there is a significant relationship between compensation and job satisfaction. Based on the explanation that has been described can be concluded that the compensation effect on job satisfaction.

H1: compensation effect on job satisfaction

Compensation Effect on Commitment Lecturer at the College

Compensation is one of the important factors and concern in many organizations in retaining and attracting qualified human resources (Bangun, 2012). The compensation must be based on principles of justice, where compensation can meet the needs of its employees, at least the compensation should be based on the work already done by the employee to the organization being run. This is evidenced in a study conducted by Islam et al. (2012), which revealed that the compensation positive and significant effect on the commitment of the lecturers at the college. Based on the explanations that have been described, it can be concluded that compensation can affect the commitment of lecturers at the college.

H2: compensation effect on commitment of lecturers at the college

Working Condition Effect on Job Satisfaction

Luthans (2006) working conditions are conditions to be around employees and can effect on employee to do the job, that good working conditions will affect a person's job satisfaction in the work. This is evidenced in a study conducted by Bilal (2012), which revealed that working conditions have an impact on job satisfaction. Based on the explanations that have been described, it can be concluded that working conditions can affect the job satisfaction.

H3: working conditions effect on job satisfaction

Working Condition Effect on Commitment Lecturer at the College

Research conducted by Haq et al. (2014) revealed that working conditions effect on employee commitment to the organization. Working conditions can also increase the commitment of lecturers at the college, where working conditions are comfortable and conducive, the faculty will be committed to the college and will not leave the college.

H4: working conditions effect on commitment of lecturers at the college.

Research Design

This research is a quantitative research. Collecting data using primary data obtained from questionnaires that include compensation, working conditions, job satisfaction and commitment of lecturers at the college. This study has two independent variables, namely Compensation and Working Conditions. Rivai and Sagala (2013), compensation is something that employees received in lieu of contributing their services to the company. Indicators in compensation (X1) is salary, allowance, basic award of compensation, the compensation system in an organization (college), and the difference in compensation given by an organization to other employees. According Luthans (2006) working condition is a condition that is around employees and can effect on employee to do the job. Indicators in working condition (X2) is a clean workplace, the lighting was quite good at work, conducive and comfort in the work.

This study has two dependent variable is job satisfaction and commitment of the lecturers at the college. Job satisfaction is the individual votes for a job whether pleasant or unpleasant to do (Bangun,

2012). Indicators in Job Satisfaction (Y1) is the relationship with colleagues, relations with superiors, the job itself, the promotion and the ability of employees to build on the progress that has been hired college. According to Robbins and Judge (2008), employee commitment (lecturer) in the organization is an emotional connection with employees of certain organizations to set goals and a desire to remain a member, and the achievement of the goals of the organization. Indicators in the commitment of lecturers at the college (Y2) is the willingness to work hard for college, loyalty, pride, unity of purpose and desire to remain an employee (lecturer) in the college.

The research instrument is based on indicators that will be examined, comprising: compensation, working conditions, job satisfaction and commitment of the lecturers at the college. The questionnaire will be distributed consisting of 38 points with five alternative answers questions. Researchers gave a score to each question will be awarded to lecturers with Likert scale, namely: 1 = strongly disagree (STS), 2 = disagree (TS), 3 = neutral (N), 4 = agree (S) and 5 = strongly agree (SS).

To measure each of the variables to be investigated, for variable compensation consists of 18 items taken from the question Heneman and Schwab (1985) which has been adopted in the study of Islam et.al (2012), for the commitment variable faculty consists of six of the questions taken from Mowday, Steers and Porter (1979) the researchers adopted a questionnaire conducted in the study of Islam et al. (2012), job satisfaction variables consist of 7 the questions taken from Cook et al. (1981) which has been adopted in the study of Islam et al. (2012) and working conditions 7 the questions made in the study of Islam et al. (2012).

Location of the study to be conducted in the college town of Batam, with the object of study in this research is a tenured faculty who work in college and a total population of 250 permanent lecturer of accounting and management listed on the website <http://forlap.dikti.go.id/perguruan tinggi>.

Sampling method in this research is purposive sampling. Processing data using SPSS 20. This study used a test validity and reliabilitas to test valid and reliabelnya data used. This research uses descriptive analysis to analyze the data that is used to describe the way mendeskripsikan or data that has been collected. In this study using classic assumption test consisting of multicollinearity test and test for normality, testing this hypothesis using simple regression analysis.

Results and Discussion

Characteristics of Respondent

Respondents in this study is a lecturer of accounting and management work in college Batam selected using purposive sampling based on the criteria of tenured faculty. Based on these criteria, the sample used in this study amounted to 156 respondents.

Table 1 Respon Rate.

Information	Total
Questionnaires were distributed	250
Questionnaires were return from respondent	166
Questionnaires were not content with complete	10
Total sampel	156
Respon Rate	62.40%

Based on the questionnaire that has been collected can be seen that of 156 samples used in this study, in terms of age the largest percentage shown by the age range of 25 years to 40 years, in terms of gender, the presentation of the biggest shown by men compared to women, in terms of organizational status are shown in the university, in terms of types of organizations are shown in private higher than the country, in terms of nature of work, the nature of work is permanent, in terms of qualification of lecturers, the majority of recent education is S2, in terms of experience of the organization right now, the majority of 5 years up with 10 years, and the last in terms of total experience as a lecturer, the majority being 5 years up to 10 years.

Instrument Test

Testing instrument in this study conducted on the individual indicators that an unknown variable rate and reliabel valid indicator as a measurement variable. This instrument consists of testing the validity and reliability test. Decision-making validity test considered valid if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ (Ghozali, 2012) for each question in the study of $r_{count} > r_{table}$ is used, it can be concluded that the questions in the questionnaire considered valid.

Reliability test in this study said to be reliable if the coefficient of reliability (Cronbach alpha-value) is greater than 0.60 (Ghozali, 2012). Compensation with a Cronbach alpha-0895, the working conditions with a Cronbach alpha-0883, job satisfaction with a Cronbach alpha-0795, and committed lecturers with Cronbach alpha-0830. All variable-Cronbach alpha values greater than 0.60, so it can be concluded that all variables used in this study is reliable.

Table 2 Respondents Answer Frequencies to Compensation's Variable

Indikator	Frekuensi Jawaban Responden										Total
	STS	%	TS	%	N	%	S	%	SS	%	
P1	3	1.90%	27	17.30%	39	25.00%	79	50.60%	8	5.10%	156
P2	1	0.60%	37	23.70%	33	21.20%	76	48.70%	9	5.80%	156
P3	2	1.30%	30	19.20%	37	23.70%	74	47.40%	13	8.30%	156
P4	8	5.10%	32	20.50%	43	27.60%	58	37.20%	15	9.60%	156
P5	2	1.30%	28	17.90%	39	25.00%	71	45.50%	16	10.30%	156
P6	2	1.30%	35	22.40%	39	25.00%	68	43.60%	12	7.70%	156
P7	5	3.20%	38	24.40%	52	33.30%	54	34.60%	7	4.50%	156
P8	2	1.30%	30	19.20%	42	26.90%	70	44.90%	12	7.70%	156
P9	1	0.60%	27	17.30%	40	25.60%	69	44.20%	19	12.20%	156
P10	2	1.30%	32	20.50%	41	26.30%	72	46.20%	9	5.80%	156
P11	2	1.30%	31	19.90%	42	26.90%	69	44.20%	12	7.70%	156
P12	7	4.50%	41	26.30%	47	30.10%	48	30.80%	13	8.30%	156
P13	2	1.30%	25	16.00%	42	26.90%	72	46.20%	15	9.60%	156
P14	3	1.90%	33	21.20%	47	30.10%	63	40.40%	10	6.40%	156
P15	0	0.00%	36	23.10%	47	30.10%	63	40.40%	10	6.40%	156
P16	3	1.90%	22	14.10%	52	33.30%	64	41.00%	15	9.60%	156
P17	7	4.50%	24	15.40%	41	26.30%	68	43.60%	16	10.30%	156
P18	3	1.90%	27	17.30%	43	27.60%	65	41.70%	18	11.50%	156

Sumber: hasil olahan Spss 20

According to the Table 2, the variable compensation is measured by 18 indicators and it can be seen that the respondents perceive that the respondent compensation received was good. Can be seen from the answers of respondents who tend to choose to agree with statements regarding the compensation of respondents received from their place of work.

Table 3 Respondents Answer Frequencies to Working Condition's Variable

Indikator	Frekuensi Jawaban Responden										Total
	STS	%	TS	%	N	%	S	%	SS	%	
P1	15	9.60%	50	32.10%	38	24.40%	49	31.40%	4	2.60%	156
P2	12	7.70%	50	32.10%	40	25.60%	48	30.80%	6	3.80%	156
P3	6	3.80%	35	22.40%	48	30.80%	63	40.40%	4	2.60%	156
P4	9	5.80%	51	32.70%	54	34.60%	37	23.70%	5	3.20%	156
P5	10	6.40%	80	51.30%	38	24.40%	21	13.50%	7	4.50%	156
P6	11	7.10%	67	42.90%	46	29.50%	29	18.60%	3	1.90%	156
P7	14	9.00%	66	42.30%	42	26.90%	33	21.20%	1	0.60%	156

Sumber: hasil olahan Spss 20

Based on Table 3, the variable working conditions measured with 7 indicator and it can be seen that the respondents perceive the working conditions of respondents received was enough to contribute well to the respondents. Can be seen from the answers of respondents who tend to choose to disagree with statements regarding the working conditions they feel.

Table 4 Respondents Answer Frequencies to Job Satisfaction's Variable

Indikator	Frekuensi Jawaban Responden										Total
	STS	%	TS	%	N	%	S	%	SS	%	
P1	1	0.60%	11	7.10%	38	24.40%	94	60.30%	12	7.70%	156
P2	5	3.20%	9	5.80%	31	19.90%	93	59.60%	18	11.50%	156
P3	0	0.00%	8	5.10%	26	16.70%	96	61.50%	26	16.70%	156
P4	1	0.60%	10	6.40%	39	25.00%	89	57.10%	17	10.90%	156
P5	2	1.30%	19	12.20%	38	24.40%	84	53.80%	13	8.30%	156
P6	1	0.60%	7	4.50%	41	26.30%	92	59.00%	15	9.60%	156
P7	2	1.30%	9	5.80%	33	21.20%	94	60.30%	18	11.50%	156

Sumber: hasil olahan Spss 20

Based on Table 4, the variables measured job satisfaction working with 7 indicator and it can be seen that the respondents perceive the job satisfaction of respondents received was good. Can be seen from the answers of respondents who tend to choose to agree with statements regarding the job satisfaction they feel

Table 5 Respondents Answer Frequencies to Commitment Lecturer at the College Variable

Indikator	Frekuensi Jawaban Responden										Total
	STS	%	TS	%	N	%	S	%	SS	%	
P1	1	0.60%	7	4.50%	20	12.80%	104	66.70%	24	15.40%	156
P2	6	3.80%	44	28.20%	32	20.50%	59	37.80%	15	9.60%	156
P3	6	3.80%	29	18.60%	56	35.90%	52	33.30%	13	8.30%	156
P4	4	2.60%	20	12.80%	40	25.60%	76	48.70%	16	10.30%	156
P5	0	0.00%	5	3.20%	32	20.50%	95	60.90%	24	15.40%	156
P6	11	7.10%	24	15.40%	54	34.60%	52	33.30%	15	9.60%	156

Sumber: hasil olahan Spss 20

Based on Table 5, the variable lecturer at the college's commitment is measured by 6 indicators and it can be seen that the respondents perceive the commitment of respondents feel is quite good. Can be seen from the answers of respondents who tend to choose to agree with the statement about the commitment they feel.

Table 6 Test multicollinearity

variable	tolerance	VIF
Compensation	0.972	1.029
Working conditions	0.972	1.029

Based on Table 5, each variable has a value of tolerance > 0.10 and VIF < 10, so that it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in this regression model.

Table 7 Normality Test

Residual unstandardized	
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	1119
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0164

According to the table above, the value of Kolmogorov-Smirnov was 1119 and 0164 the value of their significance. The significance value greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the data were normally distributed residuals.

Table 8 Simple Linear Regression Tested 1

Model	Unstand. Coeff.	Stand. Beta	t	Sig	R ²
	B	Err			
Constant	12.693	1.305	9.727	0.000	
Compensation	0.221	0.021	0.642	10.399	0.000

According to the Table 8, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$JS = 12.693 + 0.221 COM$$

The results of hypothesis testing 1 shows the count of 10.399 t with a significance value of 0.000. The significance value under 0.05 so it can be concluded that the h1 supported. This means there is influence between compensation on job satisfaction.

According to the table above, the value of the coefficient of determination in this study for 0.413. This indicates that compensation (X1) can explain job satisfaction (Y1) amounted to 41.30%, while 58.70% is explained by other variables outside this research model.

Table 9 Simple Linear Regression Tested 2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Beta	T	Sig	R ²
	B	Std. Error				
	Constant	11.623				
Compensation	0.155	0.020	0.553	7.820	0.000	0.284

According to the table 9 above, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$CL = 11.623 + 0.155 COM$$

The results of the hypothesis test showed t count 2 of 7.820 with a significance value of 0.000. The significance value under 0:05 so we can conclude that h2 supported. This means striving towards a commitment compensation lecturer at the college.

According to the table above, the value of the coefficient of determination in this study amounted to 0.284. This indicates that compensation (X1) can explain the commitment of lecturers at the college (Y2) amounted to 28.40%, while 71.60% is explained by other variables outside this research model.

Table 10 Simple Linear Regression Tested 3

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Beta	T	Sig	R Square
	B	Std. Error				
	Constant	30.148				
Working Conditon	0.210	0.069	-0.237	-3.034	0.003	0.056

According to the table 10 above, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$JS = 30.148 + - 0.210 WC$$

Results of the third hypothesis showed t count of -3.034 with a significance value of 0.003. The significance values below 0.05, so it can be concluded

that h3 supported which means there is influence between the working conditions on job satisfaction.

According to the table above, the value of the coefficient of determination in this study for 0.056. This shows that the working conditions (X2) can explain job satisfaction (Y1) amounted to 05.60%, while 94.40% is explained by other variables outside this research model.

Table 11 Simple Linear Regression Tested 4

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Beta	T	Sig	R ²
	B	Std. Error				
	Constant	22.871				
Working Conditon	-0.096	0.060	-0.127	-1.595	0.113	0.016

According to the table above, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$KD = 22.871 + -1.595 WC$$

The results of the fourth hypothesis showed t count of -1.595 with a significance value of 0.113. The significance value above 0.05 so it can be concluded that h4 is not supported properly, which means there is no influence between the working conditions of the commitment lecturer at perguruan height.

According to the table above, the value of the coefficient of determination in this study for 0056. This shows that the working conditions (X2) can explain the commitment of lecturers at the college (Y1) amounted to 01.60%, while 98.40% is explained by other variables outside this research model.

Compensation Effect on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been outlined above, indicate that the first hypothesis is supported, which means that there is influence between compensation on job satisfaction. This is supported by the frequency of respondents to variable compensation and job satisfaction which are inclined to agree in the case of lecturers receive compensation and job satisfaction in Batam. This marks the compensation awarded by the college very well received by lecturer who work at colleges Batam and can affect job satisfaction of the lecturers. The results of this study also supported the theory put forward by Maslow if it is associated with the characteristics of the respondent, in this study the authors found a lecturer whose age ranges from 25 years to 40 years where the range of that age lecturers want high compensation that satisfaction lecturer in work increases, if satisfaction lecturer job increases, the

work of a lecturer at the college will be optimal. The results are consistent with research conducted by Islam et al. (2012), Neog and Barua (2014), Sari (2009), Bilal (2012) who found that compensation effect on job satisfaction.

Compensation Effect on Commitment Lecturer at the College

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been outlined above, indicate that the second hypothesis is supported, which means that there is influence between the compensation of the commitment lecturer at the college. This is also supported by the respondent's answers to variable compensation and commitment of lecturers at the college tend to choose to agree on every question. This indicates that the high compensation received by the lecturers will increase the commitment of the lecturers at the college, when the compensation level lower acceptable lecturer commitment for lecturers at universities will be weakened, and lecturers will be working elsewhere to employ a lecturers with compensation levels lecturers expect. The results of this study are consistent with the Nawab and Bhatti (2011) and Islam et al. (2012), suggesting the influence of compensation on the commitment of lecturers at the college.

Working Condition Effect on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been outlined above, indicate that the third hypothesis is well supported, which means that there is influence between the working conditions on job satisfaction. This is supported by the respondent's answers on working conditions, in which respondents were more likely to choose to disagree, indicating that the working conditions they feel well enough to contribute. While the respondents answers to job satisfaction are more likely to choose to agree to satisfaction in the work that lecturers feel. If the working conditions are good (eg clean and comfortable working conditions), people will more easily complete their work and can increase job satisfaction (Luthans, 2006). In this study, working conditions perceived by the lecturers were very good (working conditions clean, adequate lighting, conducive and comfort in the work) is thus a good working condition will improve job satisfaction and can complete the work provided by the college well. If the working conditions of lecturers feel bad (working

conditions that are not clean, not enough light, uncomfortable and not conducive) the job satisfaction of the lecturers will weaken and affect the level of completion of the work will be done on the faculty of the college. The research result is in line with research conducted by Bilal (2012). This indicates that the working conditions of employees considered in the work.

Working Condition Effect on Commitment Lecturer at the College

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been outlined above, indicate that the fourth hypothesis is not supported properly, which means there is no influence between the working conditions of the commitment lecturers at the college. This indicates that a good working conditions (working conditions clean, adequate lighting, conducive and comfort in the work) there is no effect on commitment lecturers at the college. Thus, commitment lecturers at the college is not determined on the working conditions in the work. If offered the job lecturers who have income (compensation) higher than the previous college's commitment lecturer at the college will be unshaken and lecturer will move to the colleges that offer income (compensation) is quite high from the previous college. Working conditions is not a benchmark in terms of commitment lecturer at the college. This study is not consistent with research conducted by haq et al (2014), states that working conditions effect on the commitment of the organization.

Conclusion

Based on the results of research on compensation and working conditions on job satisfaction and commitment lecturer at the college, there are four hypothesis in which the three hypothesis supported and one hypothesis is not supported, it can be concluded that in accordance with the formulation of the problem, as following:

1. Compensation effect on job satisfaction. This indicates that the compensation provided by the college so have influence on job satisfaction of faculty in terms of work.

2. Compensation effect on commitment of lecturers at the college. This indicates that the compensation provided by the college will effect the commitment of lecturers at the college.

3. Working conditions effect on job satisfaction. This indicates that a good working conditions (working conditions clean, adequate lighting, conducive and comfort in the work) greatly impact the lecturer satisfaction in work.

4. Working conditions does not effect on commitment of the lecturers at the college. This indicates that a good (clean working conditions, ample lighting, conducive and comfort in the works) are not indicative of lecturer committed to working within the college in height due to the compensation factor is very important in terms of commitment lecturer at the college. If offered the job lecturers who have income (compensation) higher than the previous college's commitment lecturer at the college unshaken and lecturer will be moved to the colleges that offer a high enough income from the previous college.

This study was conducted to be used as information that is useful for college could increase job satisfaction and commitment lecturer at the college, so that lecturers work can work as much as possible and get a good work. For further research is recommended to use a sample from the same sample type or extend the sample and can add several variables that can effect on job satisfaction and commitment of the lecturers at the college to use a sample from the same sample type or extend the sample and can add several variables that can effect on job satisfaction and commitment of the lecturers at the college.

References

- Bangun, W. (2012). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung: Penerbit Erlangga.
- Bilal, H. (2012). Job Satisfaction of University Teachers : Impact of Working Conditions and Compensation. *Review Integrative Business and Economics*.
- Ghozali, I. (2012). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 20*. Semarang.
- Haq, M. A., Jindong, Y., Hussain, N., & Anjum, Z. Z. (2014). Factors Affecting Organizational Commitment Among Bank Officers In Pakistan. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*.
- Islam, T., Ahmad , Z., Ahmed, i., Ahmad, A., Saeed, M., & Muhammad, S. K. (2012). Does Compensation and Demographical Variable Influence on Teacher Commitment and Job Satisfaction? A Study of University of the Punjab, Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*.
- Johan, R. (2002). Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Dalam Lingkungan Institusi Pendidikan. *Jurnal Pendidikan Penabur*.
- Luthans, F. (2006). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi.
- Milkovich, G. T., Newman, J. M., & Gerhart, B. (2011). *Compensation* (Tenth Edition ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Nawab, S., & Bhatti, K. K. (2011). Influence of Employee Compensation on Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction : A Case Study of Educational Sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*.
- Neog, B. B., & Barua, M. (2014). Factors Influencing Employee's Job Satisfaction : An Empirical Study Among Employees of Automobile Service Workshops in Assam. *Industrial, Financial & Business Management*.
- Republik Indonesia. (2005). Undang-Undang No. 14 Tahun 2005 tentang Guru dan Dosen. Jakarta: Sekretariat Negara.
- Rivai, V., & Sagala, E. J. (2013). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- Rizal, M., Idrus, S. M., Djumahir, & Rahayu, M. (2014). Effect of Compensation on Motivation, Organizational Commitment, and Employee Performance (Studies at Local Revenue Management in Kendari City). *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*.
- Robbins, P. S., & Judge, T. A. (2008). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: Penerbit Salemba Empat.
- Sari, E. (2009). Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Iklam Organisasi terhadap Kepuasan Kerja. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi dan Organisasi*.